

Soundscape recording techniques for ecologically valid lab studies

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Mic arrays 360° soundscape recording

- Soundscape evaluation in VR requires 3D sound recording using a head-tracking-ready microphone array.

Ambisonic microphone systems

Pros

- Compact & easy to carry
- Easy 360° head-tracking
- Flexible decoding to various loudspeaker arrays

Cons

- Narrow listening area
- Tonal colouration
- Compromised spaciousness and naturalness

First-order Ambisonics (FOA)
Higher-order Ambisonics (HOA)

Spaced microphone arrays

Pros

- Wider listening area
- More spacious and natural sounding than Ambisonics
- Flexible choice of capsules (potentially a better sound quality)

Cons

- Heavier
- Could be more expensive
- Require specific loudspeaker arrays for reproduction

ESMA-3D

ORTF-3D

Equal Segment Mic Array 3D (ESMA-3D)

- 8-channel array of directional mics in a 50cm x 50cm square layout (Lee 2019).
- Horizontally spaced, vertically coincident.
→ Compact enough for outdoor rec.
→ Good downmix compatibility.
- Horizontal and vertical spacings based on time-level psychoacoustic model (Lee et al. 2017).
- Accurate 360° localisation in both loudspeaker and binaural reproductions.
- Provide spacious and natural soundscape images.

- At least 9dB channel separation is needed between the main and height microphones to ensure stable vertical localisation (Wallis and Lee 2017). → Vertical subtended angle of 90° or larger required.

Subjective evaluations

- Comparison between ESMA and First-order Ambisonics (FOA) for sport recording in 8-channel 3D loudspeaker reproduction (Moulson and Lee 2019)
- ESMA provides a greater sense of **Presence** and **Listener Envelopment** than FOA.

- Comparison between ESMA and First-order Ambisonics for urban traffic sounds in 360° VR (Head mount display + 8-channel 3D loudspeaker playback) (Lee and Price 2021)
- ESMA provides better **Plausibility** and **Robustness** than FOA.
- These results might be related to **Ecological Validity** (to be investigated further).

Soundscape recordings using ESMA-3D

Open access recording database

[10.5281/zenodo.3549049](https://zenodo.org/record/3549049)

References

- Wallis, R. & Lee, H. "The Reduction of Vertical Interchannel Crosstalk: The Analysis of Localisation Thresholds for Natural Sound Sources," *Applied Sciences*, 7, 3, 20 p. 278, 2017.
- Lee, H., Johnson, D. & Mironovs, M. "An Interactive and Intelligent Tool for Microphone Array Design," Presented at the 143rd Audio Engineering Society Convention, 2017.
- Lee, H. "Capturing 360° Audio using an Equal Segment Microphone Array (ESMA)," *Journal of the Audio Engineering Society*, 67, 1/2, p. 13-26, 2019.
- Moulson, A. & Lee, H. "The influences of microphone system, video and listening position on the perceived quality of surround recording for sport content," Presented at the 147th Audio Engineering Society Convention, 2019.
- Lee, H. & Price, H. "Comparison between ESMA and first-order Ambisonics for urban soundscape recording and reproduction in 360° VR", in preparation, 2021.